

Editorial

It is my sincere hope that, to the stalwart readership of *Early Music Performer*, the rebranding of the National Early Music Association's (NEMA) journal to *Early Music Performance & Research* will not come as too much of a shock to the system. It has been both a great pleasure, and a distinct learning curve, taking the reins from my predecessor, Andrew Wooley, who successfully guided the journal for thirteen years across 28 issues, and I hope my tenure will continue the successes achieved by those before me, and facilitate a smooth transition into the fast-changing world of academic journal publication.

As many readers will be aware, NEMA has now moved to a subscriberless model of funding, which has, amongst other things, necessitated a move away from print publication. Whilst some may view this as a detriment, I hope that this development in the life of the journal will prove to be a significant positive. The separation from the limitations of the print medium will manifest in myriad ways, not least through the immediate lack of physical page limits. Higher-resolution images of manuscripts can be provided in-journal, allowing for the reader to observe the historic materials on which we rely in greater detail than ever before. Additionally, a digital format allows us to integrate resources in a way that is simply not possible with print: links to online material can be provided and accessed with a click of the mouse; supplementary materials, such as tables of manuscript contents, full modern editions of pieces discussed, recordings of the music, can be provided either as separate downloads or at the end of the article/issue. As technology continues to plough forward, this new digital format allows us to follow closely behind, and embrace innovation as it arrives.

The current climate of music in the UK, academic or otherwise, is fraught. One needs only look to the several recent news items: from various opera companies having their funding either cut substantially or entirely; the BBC attempting (and, in light of significant public backlash, fortunately failing) to cut the BBC Singers; or that Oxford Brookes University plans to cut its entire music programme with almost immediate effect, ensuring the jobs of only a skeleton department to see out those students currently enrolled. The sector as a whole is in dire straits, and I feel that we have a collective responsibility to prove the overall worth

of the subject, be that in schools, universities, or in professional spheres. We must be more inclusive and innovative, and show that we are willing to adapt with the times, both in the small scale—by, for instance, working to achieve a greater gender parity in the editorial board of this journal—and in a grander sense across the board.

To further these ends, the move to a digital format allows us to make the journal completely open-access, with no fiscal barriers to authors or readers right from the point of publication. This will accompany an effort to gradually make the *EMP* back-catalog available too, and to create appropriate metadata to allow the journal to be searched and accessed via institutional and academic search engines – providing better access for all readers, as well as making the prospect of contributing to the journal a more appealing one.

Following this theme of renewal and looking to the future, we have decided to broaden the remit of the journal, to include a wider aspect of research into early music, not just focusing on performance. However, for anyone in doubt, or with reservations on this move, I want to assure you all that we are still striving to present excellent content pertaining to the performance of early music – with some exciting plans already in the works for future issues. I look forward to my tenure with great anticipation, and hope that we can continue to engage and satisfy our existing audience, as well as invite new readers into the community.

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